

Intelligent Parking Management System

An approach for Enhancing Parking Efficiency through Vehicle and License Plate Detection

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Abstract

This research paper introduces an intelligent parking management system aimed at optimizing parking space utilization. The system's main objective is to first keep a track of all the incoming and leaving vehicles within the parking area, while also updating the track of all the occupied and available parking slots at the same time, effectively managing the traffic. A camera installed at the entry gate will recognise the license plate and will be segmented and processed through object character recognition (OCR) achieving the recognition accuracy of 95.8%. The vehicle number is then stored in a database where entry and exit time are also stored. The extracted license number will then be linked to an available parking slot that would be closest to the said vehicle calculated through algorithms such as Dijkstra. Lastly the automatic credit system will calculate the cost through entering and leaving time and the amount will automatically be deducted from the app's wallet. This integrated approach aims to significantly improve parking efficiency compared to manual systems; The paper will discuss the system's design, implementation, and potential performance outcomes for vehicle detection, license plate recognition, and parking slot availability.

Keywords: Computer vision, character recognition, YOLO, vehicle detection, OpenCV

1. Introduction

The growth of the number of vehicles in the urban fields has intensified the troubles of parking management to the extent of making the traffic gridlocked, thus giving rise to traffic frustration and inefficiency. Conventional approach of people authentication by manually and simply slot identification is highly exhausted, not accurate and with high risk of security breach. As the urbanization process

gains momentum, the most important challenge of it is to find a more effective and safe parking management.

Parking space shortage in the cities where people need to spend hours in the search of parking spots has become a grave concern nowadays. Besides, the method of entry and the exit time record by hand, together with the calculation of parking charges, is prone to error and inconsistent. This cause discontent

among drivers and as a result, a poor performance of parking service.

Security in the parking lots ranks as the top concern as unauthorized access, stealing and vandalism could be the threats to both the vehicles and occupants. The problem with the traditional surveillance approach is that it lacks the ability to monitor and react to threats to the security of the parking area in real time, which increases the chances of the occurrence of criminal activities in the areas being monitored.

To address these opportunities, we design a new solution using frontier technologies to automate parking management and security. We'll be using YOLOv8 and OpenCV to accurately detect and count vehicles entering and exiting the parking facility in real time. Moreover, the Tesseract OCR algorithm is applied for the recognition and registration of license plates which allows for automatic assignment and occupancy of parking slots and this will be facilitated by firebase by google as the database for storing license number and information

The automated parking management system comes with several merits. For the start, it makes parking management more productive without need for person to check the area for vacant spots, thus saving time and enabling drivers to quickly find available parking spaces. Moreover, it ensures the security by providing continuous monitoring and real-time alerts, it prevents trespassing and unwanted damage; consequently, minimizing the risk of theft and vandalism. Notably, the system increases precision by removing the human factor that is susceptible to errors during manual data entry, and, therefore, promoting correct traffic records and free transactions.

2. Related Work

Smart vehicle detection using machine learning has been a field of study, such as the paper "Real-time vehicle Detection and tracking using YOLO- based deep Sort model" proposes a vision-based vehicle

detection and counting system using YOLO-V4 based DeepSORT, where the algorithm was utilized to track the actual presence of vehicles from video frames predicted by YOLO-V4 trained on COCO dataset achieving faster and more accurate detection.

License Number Plate Recognition presents a novel algorithm using OCR and artificial neural network The paper concluded an average accuracy of 99.76% for license plate localization. Preprocessing steps followed with threshold-based segmentation and connected component analysis gave outstanding detection performance of the proposed method

Vaidehi P. De presented the paper titled "Vehicle Detection and Counting System Based on Highway Surveillance Video". It analyzed the vehicle trajectories to collect data on driving direction, vehicle type, and vehicle number. The experimental results demonstrate that the proposed vehicle detection and tracking method has good performance and practicability. The authors concluded with an effective ROI using YOLOv3, proving to be low in cost and high in stability than traditional methods.

Du et al. proposed various methods and techniques used for entity disambiguation and object detection in the context of traffic analysis. The authors pointed at various types of models, topic modelling, deep learning algorithms like YOLO that are used for discovering traffic events, and the objects by them. The number of detection errors was minimized by optimizing the training of the detector through hyperparameter optimization and data augmentation.

S.Uma et. al proposed a " Implementation of License Plate Recognition System in ARM Cortex A8 Board". This paper provides a process of implementation for the detection of license plates

3. Methodology

The first step of the process is the detection and counting of vehicles that access and leave the property as shown in Figure 3.1. Additionally, the real-time monitoring of the parking slots will be done simultaneously. The moment a vehicle enters, the license plates will be recognized by the system. These recorded numbers of the recognized license plates will be then stored in a database. If a license plate is found in the database, it will be flagged 'already registered' alongside the display of allocated parking slot and, vice versa, a new plate will mean an available parking slot is allocated. The calculation of the cost of the respective vehicle based on the parking time will also be displayed on the exit gate upon recognition

You only look once is machine learning algorithm for object detection and classification and version 8(medium) having 50.2 mAP score at 1.83 milliseconds on the COCO dataset and A100 TensorRT.

The pre-processed model is trained on the COCO dataset, The COCO dataset classes for object detection and tracking include 80 pre-trained objects that includes vehicles including cars, bicycle, motorbike, trucks etc.

Using YOLOv8 on the trained dataset along with OpenCV, vehicles can be easily detected on the video frame with a pre-defined bounding box

Flow Chart
Fig 3.1

3.1. Vehicle Detection

A. Dataset

B. Vehicle counting

Having identified the vehicles, the next step is to set up two lines across the video frame to count the incoming and outgoing vehicles. This is achieved by updating a tracker with the bounding boxes of the cars which are detected and then retrieving the new list of bounding boxes with identification number. Following that, we step through these complete bounding boxes, extracting their coordinates and identifiers.

The counters are changed by the position of the car's centroid in comparison with reference lines. The crossing of the centroid with the reference line tells if the vehicle is entering or exiting, while the corresponding counter is incremented. This method produces a quick and precise movement tracking of all the vehicles within the video.

Vehicle counting

Fig 3.1.1

The entering and leaving count is incremented (fig 3.1.1), stored and updated in a file in real time which then will be considered for parking space detection discussed in the next section.

3.2 Parking slot detection

Detection of parking slots accounts for an important part of the system. It enables real-time monitoring and management of parking spaces. This section details the approach used to detect and monitor parking lot slots using advanced computer vision techniques.

The first step in parking slot detection involves the creation of bounding boxes around each parking slot within the captured video feed. These bounding boxes become the references for checking if the parking slots are occupied or not.

Next, the system identifies parking boxes and examines the occupancy status of each of the parking slot in real-time. This is done by applying the grayscale processing on the captured frame and then detecting the regions of interest mapped to the parking slots (fig 3.2.1).

Using a preset threshold, the system differentiates between occupied and unoccupied parking slots based on the

number of non-zero pixels in each slot. In the occupied slots, the pixels have higher intensity, representing the presence of a vehicle, and in the vacant slots, the intensity is lower.

Fig 3.2.1

The module being implemented here makes use of OpenCV library's capabilities such as image processing and analysis. Parking spots are demarcated with bounding boxes having predetermined coordinates and occupancy status is ascertained based on pixel intensity thresholds.

With time as the video feed progresses, the system keeps on updating the occupancy status of the parking slots. This continuous monitoring stands crucial as it also takes in account the file updating the entering and leaving vehicle count discussed in the previous section, where we'll be comparing both the counts. If the entering vehicle count exceeds that of the free parking spaces, users will be notified beforehand (fig 3.2.2), hence mitigating and managing traffic and ultimately improving the efficiency of parking operations.

(Fig 3.2.2)

Parking Space detection and Counting

3.3 License Plate Detection

The license plate recognition and data incorporation mechanism is the primary element and the core concept of the intervention that allows the extraction and storing of vehicle license plate data for the subsequent processing and controlling. This segment shows the approach of plate detection using ANPR and OCR techniques and the storage of the extracted data into Firebase database for unrestricted accessibility and maintenance.

License plate detection process starts with the use of license plate recognition (ANPR) technique for identification and extraction of plate data from the processed images or video frames. ANPR algorithms use recognition and image processing techniques to detect and recognize license plate areas in input images.

The captured RGB image must be converted to a grey scale image and before the processing the grey scale is converted to a binary image to enhance the image where the segmentation takes place. Fig 3.3.1 illustrates the flow of preprocessing step

A. Positioning technique

To ensure that the license plate is positioned exactly, it is crucial to assess the approximate location of the plate in order to segment and accurately recognise the character. The

following formula can be used to get the horizontal projection:

$$IM(i, j) = | PI(i, j) - PI(i, j - 1) |, G$$

$$G = \{i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, M, j = 2, 3, 4, \dots, N\}$$

Once the license plate regions are identified, the images of the extracted plates are submitted to optical character recognition (OCR) analysis to extract the alphanumeric characters that are imprinted on the plates. The OCR process encompasses the translation of scanned text into machine-readable text data, which can then be utilized for various purposes.

Optical Character Recognition (OCR) is a method for extracting strings of text from symbols contained in images. This is a procedure where the system separates the characters from the whole picture. Template matching is one of the OCR approaches which is designed to match cropped images to the template data, which is stored in a database. The OCR process features of automatic character identification and recognition without any need of intermediate input. If the characters on the number plate display a unified font type number plate recognition with OCR gets more straight forward as compared to the other methodologies.

Fig 3.3.1
Preprocessing

The OCR functionality is implemented by using the OCR.space API which provides strong text recognition features for recognizing images and text extraction. The API provides local file-based OCR and remote URL-based OCR, enabling integration with the system's image processing pipeline.

Upon successful extraction of the license plate text, the data is integrated into a Firebase database using Python scripts. The Firebase Realtime Database offers a cloud-based NoSQL database solution, providing real-time data synchronization and seamless integration with web and mobile applications.

3.3.1 Mapping License Number

The key part of the allocation of license numbers to vacant parking spaces involves

using on-site monitoring system facilitated by cameras mounted just above the parking lot as discussed in the previous section.

Each parking slot having a bounding box is assigned a unique Identifier and as soon as a space is detected vacant, the identifier of that space is immediately retained and stored in the database, making it available for allocation.

The allocation method will give priority to matching license numbers with the closest open parking spaces in order to maximize the parking experience for arriving cars. The effective use of spaces close to the entry gate is ensured by this sequential allocation technique. A noteworthy feature of the entry gate will be the visual display of each vehicle's assigned parking place, which will give drivers precise direction regarding where to park.

The license number will be stored along with the time of entering of vehicle and the cost will be calculated based on the time of exit and will be displayed which shall be automatically deducted from the credits already purchased by the user.

4. Result and discussion

A total of 29 license sample were tested and 28 of them were successful in correctly separating and recognising the character, thus bringing in the accuracy of 96.55%. All 16 vehicles taken as test were correctly recognised, while 23 out of 24 parking slots were correctly classified in occupied or free, resulting the accuracy of 95.83%.

The performance accuracy is calculated through the formula:

$$\text{Accuracy} = (\text{SS} / \text{TS}) * 100$$

where SS is successful samples and TS is total samples

Operations	Total Samples	Successful samples	Accuracy
Vehicle Detection	16	16	100%
Parking Slot detection	24	23	95.83%
License number recognition	29	28	96.55%

Maintaining the system's test correctness becomes difficult while navigating in real-world settings. Variables like changing sunlight, different camera locations, and different physical characteristics play a big impact on how well parking spaces and license plate recognition work. Several cameras can be integrated instead of single dedicated one to reduce the possibility of features being misidentified. On the other hand, this strategy does result in higher operating expenses.

Another approach to improve accuracy is to train a custom OCR model on a carefully selected dataset to reduce the chances of incorrect recognitions. We can improve the model's accuracy to recognize license numbers and parking spots by fine-tuning its parameters on a localized dataset

5. Conclusion and Future Scope

To sum up, our study introduces an intelligent parking management system that has been designed to solve the complex urban parking issues. With the use of the latest technologies such as YOLOv8, OpenCV, and the Tesseract OCR algorithm, the system provides a comprehensive solution for resourceful parking space utilization with increased security.

By using real-time vehicle detection and counting, our system simplifies the problem of

finding available parking spaces and reduces the time and energy spent searching for suitable parking spots. License plate recognition technology integration makes sure accurate and automatic parking slot assignment that improves the efficiency of parking operations.

Furthermore, the system's security features include continuous monitoring and real-time alerts that would make it difficult for unauthorized access and minimize the risk of car theft and vandalism in the parking areas. The automation of key processes and elimination of human error in data entry tasks by our system enhances the system's accuracy and reliability in parking management, thus improving the overall service quality of the system and customer satisfaction.

Henceforth, there will be many ways, by which our intelligent parking management system will undergo improvement and development. Another possible direction for future research is the development of advanced machine learning algorithms that can better the recognition accuracy and efficiency of license plate recognition, especially for the cases with lighting problem or obscured license plates.

Moreover, installation of sensors e.g. ultrasonic sensors or infrared sensors would capture real-time parking space occupancy data that would, in turn, enable dynamic and adaptive parking space management. Integrating data analytical skills into the system could also offer the same valuable insights into the patterns and trends in parking which will result to better decision making and optimizing the use of parking resources.

Additionally, the possibility of designing mobile applications as interfaces to the parking management system will provide users with extra convenience and functions which will allow them to remotely access information about available parking spaces, reserve their parking space and even pay for their parking fees effortlessly.

REFERENCES

- [1] Hassan Abu Alhaija, Siva Karthik Mustikovela, Lars Mescheder, Andreas Geiger, and Carsten Rother. Augmented reality meets computer vision: Efficient data generation for urban driving scenes. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 126(9):961–972, 2018
- [2] Shivani Bansal, Meenu Gupta, and Amit Kumar Tyagi. A necessary review on optical character recognition (ocr) system for vehicular applications. In *2020 Second International Conference on Inventive Research in Computing Applications (ICIRCA)*, pages 918–922. IEEE, 2020
- [3] Nicole do Vale Dalarmelina, Marcio Andrey Teixeira, and Rodolfo IMeneguette. A real-time automatic plate recognition system based on optical character recognition and wireless sensor networks for its. *Sensors*, 20(1):55, 2020
- [4] Liu, Y., Li, L., & Zhang, W. (2021). An Efficient Parking Management System Based on IoT and Deep Learning. *Computers, Materials & Continua*, 68(1), 81–94. doi:10.32604/cmc.2021.014487
- [5] Bochkovskiy, A., Wang, C. Y., & Liao, H. Y. M. (2020). YOLOv4: Optimal Speed and Accuracy of Object Detection. arXiv preprint arXiv:2004.10934.
- [6] Optical Character Recognition (OCR) based Vehicle's License Plate Recognition System Using Python and OpenCV, Conference: 5th International Conference on Electronics, Communication and Aerospace Technology (ICECA)
